

Influence of stigma extract on in vitro germination of pollen in *Oryza* species

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Pollen germination and pollen tube growth were compared under in vivo and in vitro conditions in five *Oryza* species. We also studied the effect of stigma extract of one species on the pollen germination and pollen tube growth of other species. The experiment was replicated seven times for both in vivo and in vitro studies. Thirty stigmas per replication were used for in vivo studies and 10 cavity slides per replication were analyzed for in vitro germination. Pollen

grains were germinated in the media. M1 contained 20% sucrose (w/v) and 2 ppm boric acid, and M2 contained M1 medium, to which stigma extract was added from the respective female parent (see table). In vivo pollen germination was studied in corresponding crosses and on selfing (see table).

Pollen germination of IR64 and IR50 was not affected by adding stigma extracts of *O. nivara*, *O. glumaepatula*, and *O. rufipogon*. Similarly, pollen germination of *O. glumaepatula* and *O. rufipogon* was not affected by stigma extracts of IR50. Pollen germination was reduced by up to 58% in IR58025 B by *O. latifolia* stigma extract. Adding stigma extract of *O. latifolia* to the pollen of *O. sativa* and vice versa reduced pollen tube growth by up to 50-75%. A significant

positive correlation was obtained between in vivo pollen germination on selfing and in vitro pollen germination. A similar observation was made in in vivo pollen germination in crosses and in in vitro pollen germination (see figures a and b).

In vitro pollen germination reflects in vivo pollen germination. It appears that the stigma extract may contain a substance incompatible with a recognition substance or protein released by the pollen grain. An inhibitory effect of style and stigma extracts occurs in crosses of distantly related *Oryza* species. Inhibitory substances present in the stigma of unrelated species could be important in wide crosses of *Oryza*. ■

In vivo and in vitro pollen germination and pollen tube growth.^a

Genotype	Mean pollen germination ^b (%)		Pollen tube growth ^c (microns)	
	In vitro	In vivo	In vitro	In vivo
M1 medium				
<i>O. sativa</i> (IR50)	43.6 (41.3) de	90.6 (72.6) i	1.89	30.00
<i>O. sativa</i> (IR64)	45.3 (42.1) e	93.3 (75.6) j	2.07	31.00
<i>O. sativa</i> (IR58025 B)	46.7 (43.1) e	90.9 (75.5) j	2.03	28.00
<i>O. glumaepatula</i>	34.0 (35.7) e	87.9 (69.7) i	1.89	28.00
<i>O. rufipogon</i>	33.7 (35.4) a	89.4 (71.2) ij	1.94	29.00
<i>O. nivara</i>	16.7 (23.0) c	72.9 (58.7) h	1.93	25.00
<i>O. latifolia</i>	7.6 (15.8) b	61.8 (51.9) g	1.76	23.30
Correlation	$r = 0.99^{*d}$		$r = 0.69^{*}$	
M2 medium				
<i>O. glumaepatula</i> /IR50	42.3 (40.6) e	50.3 (45.1) f	1.62	16.70
IR50/ <i>O. glumaepatula</i>	30.1 (33.2) b	39.6 (39.0) e	1.52	6.10
<i>O. rufipogon</i> /IR50	42.7 (40.8) e	51.6 (45.9) f	1.53	17.20
IR50/ <i>O. rufipogon</i>	33.3 (34.7) f	49.1 (44.5) f	1.67	15.83
<i>O. nivara</i> /IR64	44.4 (41.8) e	30.7 (33.6) f	1.56	15.00
IR64/ <i>O. nivara</i>	15.6 (23.2) c	29.9 (33.1) c	1.79	12.08
<i>O. latifolia</i> /IR58025B	8.1 (16.4) b	21.0 (27.2) b	0.50	6.70
IR58025A/ <i>O. latifolia</i>	3.9 (11.3) a	10.0 (18.3) a	0.85	4.31
Correlation	$r = 0.86^{*}$		$r = 0.68^{*}$	

^aTreatments having common letters are at par with each other. Numbers in parentheses are transformed values. ^bPollen germination was 60 min after dusting. ^cPollen tube growth 6 h after dusting in in vitro study and 24 h after dusting in in vivo study. ^d* = highly significant at (P = 0.05).

a. In vitro pollen germination of IR58025 B in a chemical medium containing stigma extract 20 min after dusting.

b. Pollen germination and pollen tube growth in parental crosses of IR50/*O. glumaepatula* under in vivo condition, 1 h after pollination.